

1 **Sandwich-Type Electrochemical Paper-Based Immunosensor for Claudin 7**
2 **and CD81 Dual determination on Extracellular Vesicles from Breast Cancer Patients**

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30

31 **ABSTRACT**

32 This study is focused on identifying novel epithelial markers in circulating extracellular
33 vesicles (EVs), through the development of a dual sandwich-type electrochemical paper-
34 based immunosensor for Claudin 7 and CD81 determination, as well as its validation in breast
35 cancer (BC) patients. This immunosensor allows rapid, sensitive, and label-free detection of
36 these two relevant BC biomarkers. Under optimum conditions, the limit of detection for
37 Claudin 7 was 0.4 pg mL⁻¹, with a wide linear range from 2-1000 pg mL⁻¹, while for CD81,
38 the limit of detection was 3 pg mL⁻¹, with a wide linear range from 0.01-10 ng mL⁻¹. Finally,
39 we validated Claudin 7 and CD81 determination in EVs from 60 BC patients and 20 healthy
40 volunteers, reporting higher diagnostic accuracy than the one observed with classical
41 diagnostic markers. This analysis provides a low cost, specific, versatile, and user-friendly
42 strategy as a robust and reliable tool for early BC diagnosis.

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48 **Keywords:** Claudin 7; CD81; biomarkers; breast cancer; cancer diagnosis;
49 extracellular vesicles; paper-immunosensor; electrochemical.

50

51 **INTRODUCTION**

52 Breast cancer (BC) is the most common cancer disease among females all over the
53 world. BC is the principal cause of cancer-related death in women in less developed countries
54 and the second leading cause in developed ones ¹. Clinical studies showed that early diagnosis
55 followed by suitable treatments significantly improved the survival rates ². Mammography
56 is the preferred method for BC detection; however, this method could be less effective in
57 young women with dense breasts ³. Blood-based screenings are cost-effective applications
58 for breast cancer diagnosis and, unfortunately, a reliable blood marker for accurate diagnosis
59 at early stages is not available yet ⁴. Detection of circulating proteins such as
60 carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) or cancer antigen 15.3 (CA 15-3) is actually being
61 employed without proper results in early stages. Recently, circulating tumor cells (CTCs),
62 free DNA and extracellular vesicles (EVs) have demonstrated to be very specific markers for
63 diagnosis, characterization and monitoring of cancer disease ⁵. EVs present several
64 advantages compared to other liquid biopsy components. Mainly, EVs are released in early
65 stages of cancer and their structure works as a capsule that protects the molecular and
66 proteomic cargo. Moreover, EVs isolation is a relatively fast, easy and robust method ⁶.

67 EVs are lipid-bilayered vesicles released by a variety of mammalian cells ⁷. EVs
68 enclose different types of membrane-associated proteins, and some of them are specific of
69 the cell where they were produced ⁷. Epithelial cancer cells have increased EVs release rates
70 compared to healthy epithelial cells due to tumor hypoxia ⁸, endo-lysosomal trafficking
71 disruption and cellular stress ⁹. As a consequence, the percentage of epithelial EVs isolated

72 in plasma from epithelial cancer patients is higher. Unfortunately, epithelial EVs represent a
73 very small fraction of the total of EVs found in peripheral blood and, for this reason, one of
74 the main challenges in measuring these proteins is the development of sensitive and specific
75 analytical methods ¹⁰.

76 Due to outstanding features such as superior selectivity, and sensitivity compared to
77 standard ELISA tests, electrochemical immunosensors have been quickly adopted for the
78 detection of some cancer markers ¹¹⁻¹⁵. Specifically, in the last years, paper-based
79 immunosensors have received considerable attention from the scientific community due to
80 the advantages of low cost, biocompatibility, ease of storage, portability, and the possibility
81 of performing chemical analysis using capillary flow without the need for external pumps ¹⁶.
82 Electrochemical detection is quite promising due to its compatibility with microfabrication
83 techniques, adjustable selectivity, low levels of detectability, and portability, mainly when
84 used combined with battery-powered potentiostats ¹⁷. Moreover, different techniques can be
85 explored to fabricate the electrodes on paper platforms, including sputtering, screen-printing,
86 stencil-printing, inkjet-printing, laser scribing, microwire placement, and direct drawing,
87 among others ^{13,18-20}.

88 Besides, among the least expensive of these devices are the recently introduced
89 electrochemical microfluidic paper-based analytical devices (μ PADs) ²¹⁻²⁴. μ PADs have the
90 potential to be good alternatives for point-of-care testing over traditional glass and polymer-
91 based devices since they are easy to use, inexpensive, require small volumes of reagents and
92 sample, provide rapid analysis, are disposable, can be made from renewable substrate
93 materials, and are portable ²¹⁻²³. Channel fabrication is a crucial step in the development of
94 an effective μ PAD. The fabrication of a hydrophobic barrier is a common method to define

95 channels in paper devices, and several techniques have been presented in the literature, such
96 as photolithography, wax printing, screen printing, inkjet printing, among others²¹⁻²⁴.

97 Recently, different kinds of materials have been employed for the fabrication of
98 electrodes and channel surface modifications of μ PAD for biomolecules immobilization
99^{14,24,25}. Accordingly, conductive metal nanoparticles and carbon-based materials such as
100 carbon nanotubes or graphene are commonly used. Graphene is a carbon allotrope that has
101 attracted the attention of the scientific community in recent times. This material exhibits
102 excellent mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties, and can be used to make electronic
103 devices for a variety of applications, including sensors²⁶. As for the modification of the inner
104 channel surface, SBA-15 is an Ordered Mesoporous Silica (OMS) that has attracted intense
105 interest due to its large surface area, well-defined pore structure, inertness, no toxicity, high
106 biocompatibility, and thermal and hydrothermal stability, which makes this material an
107 excellent immobilization platform for biomolecules²⁷.

108 A variety of μ PAD designs have been developed for some cancer biomarkers
109 applications. Sun and co-workers (2018) reported a novel rotational paper-based analytical
110 device to implement multi-step electrochemiluminescence immunoassays²⁸. This method
111 was applied to carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and prostate-specific antigen (PSA)
112 detection. In addition, the rotational valves are reusable and the response time can be
113 shortened to a few seconds, conferring significant advantages to the device in multi-step
114 operations. Wang et al. (2018)²⁹ presented a novel dual-mode cytosensor based on
115 polyhedral AuPd alloy nanoparticles and three-dimensional reduced graphene oxide
116 constructed for highly sensitive detection of MCF-7 cells. This paper-based dual-mode
117 cytosensor provided a reliable pathway for sensitive detection of cancer cells in clinical
118 applications. Wei et al. (2018) developed a low cost, label-free, highly sensitive and selective

119 electrochemical aptamer sensor to detect PSA in serum samples using a disposable μ PAD³⁰.
120 The authors proposed this method as a new platform for sensitive and point-of-care diagnosis
121 of prostate cancer.

122 In this work, a high throughput proteomic analysis of EVs isolated from 7 BC patients
123 and 5 healthy donors was performed by reverse phase proteomic array (RPPA) technology
124 in order to identify an epithelial marker candidate to be validated in a larger cohort of patient
125 and healthy volunteers. After the identification of Claudin 7 as epithelial marker and CD81
126 as housekeeping, we developed a dual sandwich-type electrochemical paper-based
127 immunosensor for both markers. Finally, the novel biomarker Claudin 7 was demonstrated
128 to be useful for diagnosis of early stages of breast cancer from results of experiments carried
129 out in circulating EVs from a cohort of 60 early BC patients and 20 healthy donors. To the
130 best of our knowledge, no study based on the present analytical methodology for breast
131 cancer diagnosis on EVs samples has been reported.

132

133 **EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

134 All materials, reagents, apparatus and patients characteristics are shown in the
135 Supporting Information (1).

136

137 **EVs Isolation and Sample Preparation**

138 EVs were obtained from plasma of BC and healthy donors. Plasma was obtained from
139 freshly drawn blood using separate plasma tubes. Aliquots of each plasma sample were deep-
140 frozen at storage using liquid nitrogen. All plasma samples were transported to the laboratory
141 on dry ice within 24 h.

142 EVs were isolated with qEV columns (IZON, New Zealand) by size exclusion
143 chromatography (SEC), according to the manufacturer's recommended protocol. Eluted
144 fractions enriched in EVs were concentrated by Nanosep centrifugal devices with 300 kD
145 membranes (Pall Corporation, USA). Then, the obtained EVs were lysed with 50 μ L of lysis
146 buffer containing 1 % Triton X-100, 50 mmol L⁻¹ Hepes pH 7.40, 150 mmol L⁻¹ NaCl, 1.5
147 mmol L⁻¹ MgCl₂, 1 mmol L⁻¹ EGTA, 100 mmol L⁻¹ NaF, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na pyruvate, 1 mmol
148 L⁻¹ Na₃VO₄, 10 % glycerol, and a cocktail of protease and phosphatase inhibitors (Roche
149 Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). Samples were kept at -80 °C until future analysis.

150

151 **Characterization of Plasma isolated EVs**

152 Isolated EVs were characterized following the International Society of Extracellular
153 Vesicles (ISEV) recommendations ³¹: Identification of specific EVs by specific markers
154 (CD81 and HSC70) and lack of negative marker (GM130) by Western Blot (WB) ³², single
155 vesicles analysis by Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA) and Transmission Electron
156 Microscopy (TEM). The detailed procedure is shown in the Supporting Information (2).

157

158 **Candidate Marker's Identification by RPPA**

159 EVs samples obtained from BC patients (n=7) and healthy donors (n=5) were
160 submitted to the Proteomic facilities of the MD Anderson Cancer Institute (Texas, USA)
161 following the facilities requirements in order to identify a candidate epithelial marker to be
162 validated as diagnostic marker of early BC. Samples were analyzed in a single slide,
163 according to pre-established protocols ³³. RPPA procedures are summarized in the
164 Supporting Information (3).

165

166 **ELISA Analysis**

167 ELISA determinations were performed according to specific supplier's
168 recommendations for Claudin 7 (LSBIO, USA) and CD81 (Biorbyt, UK).

169

170 **Electrochemical Device Fabrication**

171 A dual electrochemical immunosensor device was fabricated to validate the
172 biomarker candidate. It consists of a microfluidic paper-based device, where the channels
173 were fabricated by wax printing, while the electrodes were printed with graphene oxide (GO)
174 and silver ink.

175 The GO suspension was obtained from graphite powder according to the Hummer's
176 method with some modifications³⁴, and the GO ink was fabricated according to a previously
177 reported method including several modifications²⁶. Brief descriptions of these procedures
178 are summarized in the Supporting Information (4, 5).

179 The fabrication of the electrochemical paper-based device was performed according
180 to a previously reported method²⁰, with slight modifications. Firstly, two electrochemical
181 cells (containing working, auxiliary, and reference electrodes) were printed in one side of a
182 20 x 40 mm Whatman paper # 1 (one electrochemical cell for each channel) (Figure 1). The
183 working and auxiliary electrodes were printed using the GO ink over a silver ink track. The
184 Ag-pseudo reference electrode was printed using silver ink. The layout of the device was
185 prepared using the Corel Draw software. The electrodes consisted of squares with 2 mm side,
186 and the electrodes connections were made by painting with silver ink in order to ensure the
187 electrical contact with the electrochemical workstation. The electrochemical reduction of GO
188 to reduced graphene oxide (rGO) was performed according to a previously reported method
189³⁵. Briefly, the electrode was biased at a fixed potential (-1.4 V) in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ PBS for 900

190 s. Then, the rGO modified electrode was washed with milli-Q water, followed by a dry step
191 with N₂.

192 The μ PAD channels were fabricated on the same side of the paper by wax printing
193 technique¹⁹. The channels were designed using Corel Draw, and the hydrophobic barriers
194 were delimited by wax over the previously printed electrodes. The device consists of one
195 inset and one outlet connected by two parallel channels (each used to detect one biomarker)
196 with a 3 mm width and 20 mm length. After printing, the paper was heated at 90 °C for 5 min
197 to achieve homogenization of the hydrophobic walls. Then, in order to generate aldehyde
198 groups in the paper for the next step (modification of the paper channel surface), its surface
199 was treated with O₂ plasma for 1 min³⁶.

200

201 **Modification of the Paper Channel Surface**

202 SBA-15³⁷ and amino-functionalized SBA-15³⁸ were synthesized according to
203 previously reported procedures (Supporting Information (6)). The synthesized amino-
204 functionalized SBA-15 at 1.5 mg mL⁻¹ concentration was immobilized on the paper channel
205 surface (immobilization zone) through covalent binding between aldehyde groups on the
206 paper and the amino groups of the SBA-15 microparticles, as shown in Figure 1. Firstly, 10
207 μ L of 5 % glutaraldehyde in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ phosphate buffer pH 8.00 were placed in the channel
208 for 2 h at room temperature. In this step, the amino groups present in the SBA-15 surface
209 react with aldehyde groups of glutaraldehyde, leaving aldehyde groups free to interact with
210 the amino groups present in the capture antibodies. Later, 10 μ g mL⁻¹ anti-Claudin 7 and anti-
211 CD81 solutions prepared in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ PBS were incubated in their respective
212 immobilization zones in the channel for 12 h at 4 °C. The platform generated by such
213 immobilization procedure was shown to be stable at least for one month at 4 °C.

214 **Analytical Procedure for Claudin 7 and CD81 Biomarkers Determination**

215 The μ PAD was washed with 0.1 mol L^{-1} PBS, followed by a blocking treatment with
216 1 % BSA for 30 min to avoid the non-specific binding on the free sites. After a washing step
217 with 0.1 mol L^{-1} PBS, $10 \mu\text{L}$ of a previously treated sample were added and incubated in a
218 humid chamber for 5 min, followed by a washing step. In this step, Claudin 7 and CD81
219 present in the sample are immunologically recognized by the antibodies immobilized in the
220 respective channel. Later, a new washing step with 0.1 mol L^{-1} PBS was carried out in order
221 to eliminate the sample excess, followed by the addition of $10 \mu\text{L}$ HRP-anti-Claudin 7 and
222 HRP-anti-CD81 mix for 5 min and a further washing step. Finally, the substrate solution (1
223 $\text{mmol L}^{-1} \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + 1 \text{mmol L}^{-1}$ 4-TBC in 0.1 mol L^{-1} phosphate-citrate buffer pH 5.00) was
224 added. HRP catalyzes the H_2O_2 chemical reduction to H_2O , with the subsequent oxidation of
225 catechol (H_2Q) to p-benzoquinone (Q), which is detected by amperometry at +100 mV on
226 the rGO working electrode (Figure 1).

227

228 **Statistical analysis**

229 Statistic differences between breast cancer patients and healthy controls were
230 determined by t-test. The linear correlation between the two variables was measured by the
231 Pearson correlation coefficient. The distribution between categorical variables was assessed
232 by the Chi-Squared test. P-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.
233 Areas under receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were employed to assess the
234 specificity and sensitivity.

235

236 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

237 **Identification of Claudin 7 in Circulating EVs in Early-Stage of Breast Cancer Patients**

238 EVs obtained from two healthy donors were characterized according to the
239 International Society of Extracellular Vesicles (ISEV) recommendations ³¹. TEM analysis
240 reported vesicles with typical morphology and size between 50 and 150 nm. Nanoparticle
241 tracking analysis (Nanosight) showed particles with 105 nm of size average (mode = 82 nm).
242 Finally, the WB analysis displayed HSC70 and CD81 specific expression on isolated EVs
243 and the absence of GM130 (Figure 2).

244 To identify biomarkers in circulating EVs of early BC diagnosed patient, EVs were
245 isolated from plasma of healthy control subjects (n=5) and patients with BC (stages II and
246 III; n=7), and subsequently analyzed by Reverse Phase Protein Array (RPPA) technology.
247 Among differentially expressed proteins, 72 were upregulated, and 113 were downregulated
248 in patients with BC (Figure 3). Claudin 7 was the most differentially expressed protein in the
249 BC patient group ($p = 9.63 \times 10^{-5}$), considering the epithelial upregulated ones. Claudin 7 is
250 an epithelial-specific protein that belongs to epithelial tight junctions (TJs), and plays an
251 important role in maintaining cell polarity and regulating cell permeability. According to
252 recent reports, Claudin 7 is overexpressed in most BC primary tissues, independently of BC
253 subtypes and clinical or pathological variables. According to our findings and bibliographic
254 information about Claudin 7, we decided to employ this protein as a candidate biomarker in
255 EVs.

256 After choosing the candidate biomarker, we focused on testing CD81 as a
257 housekeeping in EVs. CD81 is a specific marker for EVs, but unfortunately it is not expressed
258 in the 100 % of plasma EVs. To test whether this tetraspanin is suitable to correct variations
259 in loading, CD81 was analyzed by ELISA in all samples submitted to RPPA. Then, CD81
260 values were compared with the median obtained by RPPA for each sample and an excellent
261 correlation between both parameters was found (Pearson $r = 0.9991$, $p < 0.0001$) (Supporting

262 Information (7)), demonstrating that CD81 is a suitable protein for the normalization of
263 Claudin 7 expression in EVs.

264

265 **Characterization of Synthesized SBA-15**

266 SBA-15 was morphologically characterized by SEM and TEM (Figure 4). SBA-15
267 particles elongated with a $1.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ length and $400 \pm 50 \text{ nm}$ width can be noticed in the
268 SEM micrograph of the paper modified with SBA-15 (Figure 4 a). The TEM micrograph of
269 SBA-15 shows the typical hexagonal structure and pore homogeneity of this mesoporous
270 material (Figure 4 b).

271 SBA-15 N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm is shown in Figure 4 c), and the type IV
272 isotherm with a H1 type hysteresis is typical of mesoporous materials with well-defined
273 cylinder-like pore channels and with uniform pore size. The inset of Figure 4 c) shows the
274 SBA-15 pore size distribution is narrow (8 nm width).

275 SBA-15 textural properties were as follows: SBET: $890 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $V_{\mu\text{P}}$: $0.05 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$,
276 V_{PMP} : $0.55 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and V_{TP} : $1.12 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$. An FTIR study was performed to confirm the
277 SBA-15 amino functionalization and results presented in Figure 4 d) show the changes in the
278 Si-O-Si (460 cm^{-1}), N-H (690 cm^{-1}), Si-O-Si (800 cm^{-1}), Si-OH (965 cm^{-1}), C-N, Si-O-Si, Si-
279 $\text{CH}_2\text{-R}$ (1220 cm^{-1}), NH_3^+ (1555 cm^{-1}), H-O-H (1645 cm^{-1}), and -OH (3500 cm^{-1}) peaks.

280

281 **Characterization of Reduced Graphene Oxide Electrodes**

282 The morphological characterization of the rGO electrode surface was carried out by
283 SEM. Figure 5 a) shows a uniform reduced graphene oxide spread over the paper surface,
284 indicating that the ink suspension is homogeneous. Figure 5 b) shows the energy dispersive

285 spectra of I) GO and II) rGO, and the decrease in the oxygen amount in the rGO confirms
286 the reduction of oxygenated functional moities.

287 The electrochemical behavior of the rGO electrode was examined to ensure its
288 performance. Catechol was used as a probe because the electron-transfer process associated
289 with this molecule is fast and well-known. Figure 5 c) shows a cyclic voltammogram
290 recorded in 1 mmol L⁻¹ catechol + 0.1 mol L⁻¹ phosphate-citrate buffer pH 5.00 and the
291 typical reversible process corresponding to the anodic oxidation of catechol to p-
292 benzoquinone at + 414 mV, and the subsequent cathodic reduction at + 334 mV confirm the
293 excellent electrical conductivity of rGO. Moreover, a study of the scan rate influence on the
294 peak current was performed in the 25 to 200 mV s⁻¹ range (Figure 5 d). The linear relationship
295 between the peak current values and the square root of the scan rate (inset of Figure 5 d)
296 demonstrates that the catechol overall electron-transfer process over the rGO surface is mass-
297 transport-controlled.

298 The electrochemical surface area was calculated by the Randles-Sevcik equation ³⁹.

$$299 \quad I_p = 2.69 \times 10^5 AD^{1/2} n^{3/2} \nu^{1/2} C$$

300 Where I_p is the peak current in amps, A is the electrode area in cm², D is the diffusion
301 coefficient in cm² s⁻¹, n is the number of electrons transferred in the electron-transfer process,
302 ν is the scan rate in V s⁻¹, and C is the concentration in mol L⁻¹, and the value was found to
303 be 0.239 cm².

304

305 **Optimization of Experimental Parameters**

306 A systematic investigation was performed to optimize the experimental parameters
307 that affect the biomarkers determination in real samples. This was accomplished by using a

308 500 pg mL⁻¹ Claudin 7 solution, and the following parameters were studied: pH, and
309 concentration of antibody, SBA-15, and GO ink (Supporting Information (8)).

310

311 **Analytical performance for Claudin 7 and CD81 biomarkers determination**

312 Claudin 7 and CD81 biomarkers determination was carried out under the optimized
313 conditions using the dual electrochemical paper immunosensor, and the results were
314 compared with those obtained with the commercial ELISA kit for each BC biomarker. The
315 Claudin 7 calibration curve was prepared using standard solutions with concentrations
316 ranging from 0.5 to 1200 pg mL⁻¹, and a linear relationship was observed between 2 to 1000
317 pg mL⁻¹. The linear regression equation was $I \text{ (nA)} = 6.69 + 0.24 C_{\text{Claudin 7}}$, with a linear
318 regression coefficient $R = 0.998$ (Supporting Information (9)). The coefficient of variation
319 (CV %) for the determination of 500 pg mL⁻¹ Claudin 7 was 3.75 % ($n = 5$). A similar
320 calibration plot was obtained for Claudin 7 by using the ELISA kit, and the linear regression
321 equation was $A = 0.17 + 0.01 C_{\text{Claudin 7}}$, $R = 0.996$, and a CV % of 7.32 %. The correlation
322 between the results obtained by using the electrochemical paper immunosensor and the
323 reference method (ELISA) was also assessed in EVs samples of patients in a double blinded
324 experiment, which was performed by two independent researchers. Figure 6 a) shows the
325 straight line with a slope of 1.01, indicating a good correspondence between both methods.
326 The detection limit (LOD) values for the μ PAD and the commercial ELISA kit were 0.4 and
327 3.9 pg mL⁻¹, respectively. The precision of the developed method was evaluated using
328 Claudin 7 standards. The within-assay precision was tested by five measurements on the
329 same day. These analyses were repeated for three consecutive days to estimate the between-
330 assay precision. The developed immunosensor showed good precision; the CV within-assay
331 and between-assay values were below 3.96 % and 6.14 %, respectively.

332 The CD81 calibration plot was prepared using standard solutions in the concentration
333 ranging from 0.005 to 10 ng mL⁻¹. A linear relationship was observed between 0.01 and 10
334 ng mL⁻¹. The linear regression equation was $I \text{ (nA)} = 5.40 + 23.78 C_{\text{CD81}}$, with a linear
335 regression coefficient $R = 0.998$ (Supporting Information (9)). The coefficient of variation
336 (CV %) for the determination of 5 ng mL⁻¹ CD81 was 3.66 % (n = 5). Parallel measurements
337 with the ELISA test yielded a calibration plot whose linear regression equation was $A = 0.08$
338 $+ 0.26 C_{\text{CD81}}$, $R = 0.997$, and a CV % of 6.65 %. To validate the proposed immunosensor
339 method, a comparison was performed with the results of CD81 determinations obtained with
340 the ELISA test. The slope close to 1 (Figure 6 b) demonstrated a good correspondence
341 between the immunosensor and the ELISA test, providing further evidence of the reliability
342 of the proposed approach. The LOD values for the μ PAD and the commercial ELISA kit
343 were 3 and 39 pg mL⁻¹, respectively. Moreover, the precision of the method was evaluated
344 using CD81 standards. The within-assay precision was tested by five measurements on the
345 same day. These analyses were repeated for three consecutive days to estimate the between-
346 assay precision. The developed immunosensor showed good precision; the CV within-assay
347 values were below 3.78 %, and the between-assay values were below 6.12 %. Besides, a
348 lower analysis time (20 min), and a wide linear concentration range for both biomarkers were
349 noted for the μ PAD (Table 1), compared with the ELISA test.

350 Additionally, the sensor's stability was also evaluated, and this was accomplished by
351 storing the sensor for one month at 4 °C. No significant loss of sensitivity (less than 5 %)
352 was noticed after the storage compared to the response just after fabrication. Moreover, the
353 selectivity was investigated against EVs samples with other cancer biomarkers such as
354 EPCAM, EGFR, CEA and CA 15-3 in 10-fold concentrations compared to that of CD81 and
355 Claudin 7. As shown in Supporting Information (10), the presence of these interfering

356 compounds caused negligible changes in the response (less than 2 %). Hence the results
357 indicated a strong ability of the developed immunosensor to avoid interferences, which is
358 attributed to the use of monoclonal antibodies and the blocking of non-specific adsorption on
359 the surface. Finally, a comparison of both paper and SBA-15/paper platforms was carried out
360 to assess the effectiveness of using the SBA-15 material. Results shown in the Supporting
361 Information (11) clearly confirm the increased sensitivity obtained with the SBA-15/paper
362 platform owing to the enhanced surface to volume ratio.

363

364 **Validation of Claudin 7 determination and Claudin 7/CD81 ratio**

365 80 participants were recruited for validation of Claudin 7 biomarker: 20 healthy
366 volunteers and 60 BC patients (Figure 1 and Table S1). Values for Claudin 7 and the Claudin
367 7/CD81 ratio were significantly higher for patients with breast cancer [n = 60, Claudin 7
368 median 83 nA, interquartile range (IQR) 69.9-104.8 nA; mean 90.68 ± 28.4 SD; Claudin
369 7/CD81 ratio median 1.55 nA, IQR 1.22-2.19 nA; mean 1.971 ± 1.58 SD] compared to those
370 of the healthy control group [n = 20; Claudin 7 median 55 nA, IQR 29.53 – 63.3 nA; mean
371 $0.53.91 \pm 29.62$ SD; Claudin 7/CD81 ratio median 0.594, IQR 0.22-0.71, mean 0.67 ± 0.4582
372 SD] (Figure 7). These data suggest that Claudin 7 and the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio are excellent
373 biomarkers for early breast cancer diagnosis.

374 In addition, levels of Claudin 7 and the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio did not correlate with
375 the tumor's size (for Claudin 7 Pearson $r = 0.058$; $p = 0.65$ and for Claudin 7/CD81 ratio
376 Pearson $r = 0.121$; $p = 0.35$). Moreover, Claudin 7 and the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio levels
377 showed no significant correlation with age, menopause status, grade, Ki-67 and status of ER,
378 PR and Her2 ($p > 0.05$; Table 2). Similar results were obtained in a previous study, where
379 the Claudin 7 concentration was determined in the tissues of BC patients⁴⁰.

380 By analysis of Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves, an optimum
381 diagnostic cut-off of 95.75 nA was observed for Claudin 7 [Area under the Curve (AUC),
382 0.8517; 95 % confidence interval (CI) = 0.732–0.971; sensitivity at 95 % specificity, 75.13
383 %] and an optimum diagnosis cut-off of 0.9885 for the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio [AUC, 0.8908;
384 95 % CI = 0.796–0.985; sensitivity at 90 % specificity, 90 %]. In the assessment of
385 differential accuracy, Claudin 7 and the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio showed higher AUC values
386 [0.8517 ± 0.06 SD for Claudin 7 and 0.8908 ± 0.048 SD for Claudin 7/CD81 ratio] than
387 classical serum markers as Carcinoembryonic Antigen (CEA) [AUC, 0.5217 ± 0.068 SD]
388 and Cancer Antigen 15.3 (CA 15.3) [AUC, 0.7683 ± 0.0056 SD]. Indeed, as expected, the
389 Claudin 7/CD81 ratio showed slightly higher accuracy than only Claudin 7 by comparing
390 AUC values (Figure 7).

391 In this work, we have demonstrated that the identification of tumor specific markers
392 in the total bulk of circulating EVs can be useful to improve BC diagnosis⁴¹. EVs contain
393 disease-associated proteins and transport important information from the cells of origin⁴².
394 The characterization of plasma isolated EVs has two important advantages compared to
395 circulating biomarkers in total plasma. First, lipid membranes of EVs protect their cargo from
396 proteases. Moreover, a reduction in the proteome complexity of the biological fluids is
397 expected when EVs are isolated by SEC⁴³. Additionally, RPPA analysis of EVs has been a
398 remarkable tool to identify specifically EVs associated with cancer biomarkers with excellent
399 sensitivity. The focus was directed towards specific markers of epithelial tissue, but such
400 proteomic studies can identify other biomarkers. Recently, in agreement with our work,
401 Claudin 7 has been identified as a diagnostic marker in serum from colon cancer patients⁴⁴.
402 In the last years, new diagnostic methodologies and the improvement of primary antibodies
403 have facilitated identifying new proteins as a diagnostic marker. In our case, thanks to the

404 employed nanomaterials, we developed a dual immunosensor with excellent sensitivity to
405 determine both Claudin 7 and CD81. The use of paper and graphite as materials for chip
406 fabrication reduces economic cost. This kind of chips has multiple advantages such as
407 affordability, facile disposability, portability, and simple fabrication, facilitating mass-
408 production^{23,28}. Moreover, multiplexing these devices enables the simultaneous execution of
409 multiple assays on a single device without cross-contamination¹⁶. In our work, we employed
410 this dual paper chip in a validation set of 60 patients, and we demonstrated that Claudin 7
411 and the Claudin 7/CD81 ratio can drastically improve the early breast cancer diagnosis
412 compared with classical markers used in standard methodologies. Besides, the normalization
413 with CD81 guarantees that Claudin 7 variations are due to the number of epithelial EVs and
414 not caused by a change in the number of total EVs⁴⁵. We did not observe any other relation
415 with the clinical outcomes of patients and Claudin 7 determination in EVs. Curiously, the
416 release of Claudin 7 in EVs did not correlate with tumor size, possibly because the size
417 differences were not large enough. Another possible explanation is that Claudin 7 is a protein
418 involved in focal adhesion, and its release is more related to cellular reorganization than in
419 cellular growing^{46,47}. In any case, this marker should be validated in a higher number of
420 patients, different stages of the disease as locally invasive or metastatic breast cancer, and/or
421 other diseases that could be related with false positives. Besides, this methodology must be
422 validated by in-vitro, in-vivo models, or risk population screening to earlier predict BC. At
423 the moment, we can say that this analysis is highly specific, highly sensitive, simple, and
424 cheap. Future studies must demonstrate prognostic and predictive value as well as suitability
425 as a monitoring tool.

426

427 **CONCLUSIONS**

428 Based on the results of this study, we demonstrated that: (i) Circulating EVs represent
429 a valuable sample to be used in early diagnosis of BC. (ii) Claudin 7 has been identified as
430 the most significant epithelial protein expressed in EVs and validated as a BC diagnosis
431 marker. (iii) CD81 is a suitable normalizer of EVs markers in plasma, improving the accuracy
432 of Claudin7 for BC diagnosis. (iv) Both, Claudin 7, as well as, Claudin 7/CD81 ratio have
433 better accuracy than classical circulating markers as CEA and CA 15.3 for early diagnosis of
434 breast cancer.

435 We also demonstrated that our dual sandwich-type electrochemical paper-based
436 immunosensor has a shorter overall assay time (20 min) than the one usually employed in
437 the commercial ELISA test kits (270 min) for both biomarkers, with no reduction on the
438 sensitivity and specificity. Finally, the paper-based immunosensor demonstrated to be highly
439 specific (due to the use of monoclonal antibodies), sensitive (10-fold for Claudin 7 and 13-
440 fold for CD81 in comparison with their respective ELISA test), simple, and cheap (12 times
441 cheaper than the ELISA test), improving significantly the accuracy for diagnosis in early BC.

442

443 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

444 Support from Universidad Nacional de San Luis (PROICO 22/Q241), from the
445 Agencia Nacional de Promoción Científica y Tecnológica (PICT 2018-04443, PICT-2015-
446 2246, PICT-2015-1575, PICT-2014-1184 and PICT-2014-0375), from Consejo Nacional de
447 Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET) (Argentina) (PIP 11220150100004CO),
448 from GENYO, Centre for Genomics and Oncological Research: Pfizer-University of
449 Granada, Andalusian Regional Government (Granada, Spain), and the Fundação de Amparo
450 à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (FAPESP) (2019/06293-6 and 2018/08782-1) are
451 acknowledged.

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Figure captions

729 **Figure 1.** Schematic representation of the present study which includes: i) Biomarker
730 identification, ii) Design of the electrochemical paper-based immunosensor surface
731 modification, and iii) Validation of biomarkers with the designed immunosensor.

732 **Figure 2.** Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) image of isolated EVs from patients
733 after purification via size exclusion chromatography (SEC). Red arrows show lipoprotein
734 contamination while black arrows depict EVs (a). Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis of isolated
735 EVs shows particles with 105 nm of size average (mode = 82 nm), SD is represented as red
736 dot line in the graphic (b). Western blot image from cell controls and EVs lysates (c).

737 **Figure 3.** VENN diagram summarizing RPPA analysis, where 72 proteins were enriched in
738 healthy control and 113 enriched in EVs from breast cancer patients (a). Box plot showing
739 epithelial markers significantly high expressed in patients (Claudin 7 p value = 9.6×10^{-5} ,

740 Epithelial Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) p value = 2.4×10^{-4} , Estrogen Receptor (ER) p
741 value = 4.4×10^{-3} , HER3 p value = 6.1×10^{-4}) (b). Values represent concentration related to
742 the average of all samples.

743 **Figure 4.** SEM (a) and TEM (b) images of the SBA-15. N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm
744 of SBA-15 at 77 K (c). FTIR spectra of SBA-15 and amino functionalized SBA-15 (d).

745 **Figure 5.** Morphological characterization of the rGO working electrode by SEM (a), Energy
746 dispersive spectra of I) GO and II) rGO (b). Cyclic voltammogram recorded with the rGO
747 electrode in 1 mmol L^{-1} catechol + 0.1 mol L^{-1} phosphate-citrate buffer pH 5.00 at 75 mV s^{-1}
748 (c), and plot of the square root of the scan rate on the peak current (d).

749 **Figure 6.** Correlation plot between results obtained with the dual electrochemical paper-
750 based immunosensor and the commercial ELISA kit for Claudin 7 (a) and CD81 (b).

751 **Figure 7.** CEA, CA15.3, Claudin 7, and Claudin 7/CD81 levels (a, b, c and d) in plasma in
752 the validation set of patients and healthy volunteers ($n=60$ and $n=20$ respectively). ROC
753 Curves of CEA, CA15.3, Claudin 7, and Claudin 7/CD81 ratio (e, f, g and h) for the
754 assessment of diagnosis accuracy of BC.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

a)

Diferentially expressed Markers

b)

Epithelial Marker Levels

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 7

Tables

841 **Table 1.** Comparison of the analytical performance of the commercial ELISA kit and
 842 the dual electrochemical paper immunosensor (EI) for each BC biomarker.

Method	Time (Min)	CV % ^a	CV % ^a	CV % ^a	Linear range	LOD
		Within-assay	Between-assay			
ELISA _{Claudin7}	270	6.85	9.89	7.32	15.1 – 1000 ^b	3.9 ^b
EI _{Claudin7}	20	3.96	6.14	3.75	2 – 1000 ^b	0.4 ^b
ELISA _{CD81}	270	4.93	8.32	6.65	0.15 – 10 ^c	0.039 ^c
EI _{CD81}	20	3.78	6.12	3.66	0.01 – 10 ^c	0.003 ^c

843 ^a Five replicates (n = 5).

844 ^b pg mL⁻¹ claudin 7.

845 ^c ng mL⁻¹ CD 81.

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Table 2. Correlation between Claudin 7 determination and clinical relevant data of

859 enrolled patients.

	Age	Menopause status	Grade	Estrogens Receptor	Progesterone Receptor	Her2	Ki-67 (%)
Pearson r							
Claudin 7	0.077	0.141	0.058	0.101	0.0646	0.133	0.017
Claudin 7/CD81	0.067	0.101	0.121	0.033	-0.061	0.068	0.044
P Values							
Claudin 7	0.554	0.281	0.658	0.440	0.626	0.334	0.901
Claudin 7/CD81	0.610	0.439	0.356	0.802	0.645	0.621	0.749

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